

Open Science Champion

ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook

Key Revisions – December 2025

Executive Summary

We have updated the ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook to better champion the open science practices that make ASAP-funded research reusable and verifiable. Major changes include (i) Shifting the requirement to deposit data, code, protocols, and key lab materials from the time of journal publication to preprint posting, (ii) Requiring revised preprints, and (iii) Requiring data to be shared in standardized formats in discipline-specific repositories.

This document summarizes ten overarching updates made between the September 2024 and December 2025 Handbook versions, providing an explanation for each change. A comprehensive list of changes is available in the *track changes* version of the Handbook, which is shared in this Zenodo repository.

ASAP Staff will enforce the December 2025 Handbook for all CRN awards disbursed on or after **January 1, 2026**. For awards disbursed before January 1, 2026, we will support grantees in meeting the updated requirements.

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Summary of Changes

	Topic	Change
1	Deposition Timeline	Data, code, and protocols deposition required by time of preprint. Key lab material registration submitted by time of preprint.
2	Prioritize Preprints	Revised preprints required; ASAP-formatted KRT required in preprint.
3	Streamline Progress Tracking	Preprints must be on bioRxiv/medRxiv with ASAP in the funder metadata field; preprints must link to associated journal publication.
4	Data Deposition Standards	Raw data must be deposited in discipline-specific repositories; tabular data must follow Tidy Data principles.
5	Centralize Omics Data	Omics datasets must be deposited in the CRN Cloud.
6	Point-and-Click Workflows	Detailed documentation outlining point-and-click workflows is required when requested by ASAP Staff.
7	Study Registration	Study registration recommended; required when mandated by other policies and for replication studies.
8	Key Lab Material Deposition	Some grants require physical deposition of materials in addition to RRID registration.
9	AI Models	Clarification that AI models must be shared.
10	Minor edits	Edits to wording, clearer operationalization, and reorganization for better flow.

Explanation of Changes

1. Deposition Timeline

Update: Data, code, and protocols must now be deposited, and a request to register key lab materials must be submitted, by the time of preprint posting. This supersedes the previous requirement for availability by the time of publishing in a journal. (Overarching Requirement 1)

Purpose: This shift supports the principle of Lifecycle Sharing, ensuring research outputs are shared as they are produced, rather than only when results are published in a journal. In order to report results in a preprint, the data code, protocols, and key lab materials must already exist. Moreover, preprints increasingly serve as the primary vehicle for communicating scientific findings and help ensure that the research community maintains direct control over the dissemination of its findings. Thus, we now require these materials to be shared by the time of posting a preprint.

2. Prioritize Preprints

Update: The Handbook now reinforces the role of preprints as the primary vehicle for communicating research results from ASAP-funded work:

- **Revised preprints.** Grantees are required to post revised preprints that address comments from the ASAP Open Science Team and peer reviewers. (Policy item 3.1.6)
- **Deposition timeline.** As outlined in [the first update](#).
- **Preprint Key Resources Tables (KRTs).** Preprints must include a complete KRT listing identifiers for all research inputs and outputs. (Policy item 3.4.1)
- **Preprint Policy Alignment.** We signal our full alignment with the [Preprint Policy Framework](#) by explicitly requiring that authors retain copyright to their preprints. (Policy item 3.1.3)

Purpose: We aim to ensure the scholarly record, including manuscripts, data, code, protocols, and lab materials, is disseminated in a timely manner and remains under the control of the research community. We envision a system where preprints serve as the primary vehicle for disseminating research findings and where journals can offer services that improve the quality of research outputs, but these services are decoupled

from disseminating and accessing research findings (more detail [available here](#)). We aim to promote a research culture where research findings and their associated data, code, protocols, and lab materials, are shared when they are produced, rather than only at the time of publication in a journal.

3. Streamline Progress Tracking

Update: The updated policy streamlines output tracking in three ways:

- **Preprint deposition in bioRxiv or medRxiv.** We now require grantees to post preprints to bioRxiv or medRxiv and to enter Aligning Science Across Parkinson's in the recently added funder metadata field. (Policy items 3.1.1 and 3.1.4)
- **Linking preprints to journal publications.** Once a manuscript is published in a journal, we require that the associated preprint identifies the journal publication – bioRxiv and medRxiv usually do this automatically. (Policy item 3.1.5)
- **Requiring ASAP-formatted KRTs at the time of preprint.** We previously required a KRT, but accepted Cell Press and eLife formatted KRTs, which do not unambiguously identify whether a resource was newly generated. We previously required that the KRT was publicly available by the time a manuscript was published in a journal. We now require an ASAP-formatted KRT at the time of posting a preprint. (Policy item 3.4.1)

Purpose: The updates in the first and second bullet points allow us to leverage the *channel* and *activity dashboard* features in bioRxiv/medRxiv. Preprints that identify ASAP in the funder metadata field are automatically added to the [ASAP bioRxiv/medRxiv channel](#). This channel provides a publicly available list of preprints that stem from ASAP-funded research. An activity dashboard based on this channel then allows ASAP Staff to easily track preprint metadata, including dates, license, citations, downloads, grant numbers, ORCIDs, and linked journal publications. By using the bioRxiv/medRxiv channel and activity dashboard to centralize our tracking of preprints, we hope to increase the timely posting of preprints to a community-recognized repository. CRN grantees already post >95% of preprints to bioRxiv or medRxiv. Both these preprint repositories are managed by [OpenRxiv](#) – an organization dedicated to the scientific community it serves.

ASAP-formatted KRTs enable ASAP Staff to more easily combine KRTs across all CRN studies and identify which teams are generating and using specific resources.

4. Data Deposition Standards

Update: The Policy now requires that raw data be deposited to a discipline-specific repository and that tabular data are deposited in a standardized ‘Tidy’ format (Policy items 1.1.1 and 1.1.3).

Purpose: Shared data often lacks the structure and metadata necessary for others to understand it and build on it. By requiring raw data to be deposited to discipline-specific repositories, we aim to leverage the established infrastructure and associated metadata standards to ensure that data from ASAP-funded research aligns with the [FAIR Principles for data sharing](#). To facilitate compliance with these data sharing requirements, many ASAP CRN 2026 awards include a dedicated Data Manager role.

5. Centralize Omics Data

Update: Omics data collected as part of an ASAP-funded research project must be deposited to the [CRN Cloud](#). (Policy item 1.1.4)

Purpose: ASAP operates a curated, quality-controlled omics repository. We require deposition to the CRN Cloud to maximize the value of the omics data ASAP grantees collect, and to ensure curation and quality control. Many grantees already deposit data to the CRN Cloud.

6. Point-and-Click Workflows

Update: We renamed the policy item “Analyses without code”, to “Point-and-click Workflows” and made the item required, if specifically requested by ASAP Staff. (Policy item 1.2.7)

Purpose: Detailed and unambiguous documentation about non-scripted preprocessing and analysis workflows are rarely shared. While we prefer that preprocessing and analyses are scripted when possible, we recognize that not all teams are versed in this approach. We aim to prevent a double standard that would arise by implementing more stringent requirements for researchers generating scripts than for those using point-and-click workflows. Therefore, the updated policy reserves the right to request detailed documentation about point-and-click workflows.

7. Study Registration

Update: We now recommend study registration. We also explicitly state that registration is required for the types of research where other policies already require it, and for replication studies. (Policy items 1.5.1 and 1.5.2)

Purpose: Study registration remains uncommon across many of the types of research funded by the ASAP CRN. Nonetheless, registering study plans before collecting data, and registering analysis plans before analyzing data, can reduce risk of bias and improve transparency. As an initial step to socialize the practice of study registration, we integrate this practice into the policy as a recommendation.

8. Key Lab Material Deposition

Update: The updated policy clarifies that some grants *require* that key lab materials are physically deposited so that other researchers can order them. (Policy item 1.4.5)

Purpose: Some ASAP CRN awards focus on the development of key lab materials. Whereas the previous policy explicitly required that grantees register an identifier for their newly generated key lab materials, we add this conditional requirement to avoid ambiguities between grant contracts and the open science policy.

9. AI Models

Update: The updated policy explicitly states that AI models must be shared. (Policy item 1.2.5)

Purpose: We consider AI models to be a combination of code and data – which are already covered under existing policy items. To avoid ambiguity, we added AI models as a distinct policy item and link to guidance we drafted for CRN grantees.

10. Minor edits

In addition to the updates above, the updated Handbook:

- Further operationalizes some policy items.
- Reorganizes some policy items for a better flow.
- Makes minor edits throughout for clarity and readability.